

Results and Discussion

The proposed method for determining GSH with mercuric chloride is rapid, simple and accurate. The reaction conditions are not critical and accurate results are readily obtained even with microsamples. It is not necessary to prepare an organomercuric derivative which has to be used in certain other procedures⁷.

The advantage of the method is that the addition of potassium iodide to bind the unreacted Hg^{II} permits the use of phenolphthalein indicator. Indicators like methyl orange and methyl red which show a colour change on the acid side of the equivalence point, do not give satisfactory results. But these had to be used by previous workers^{13,14} in order to avoid interference due to the formation of a yellow precipitate of mercuric hydroxide formed prior to the end-point if indicators like phenolphthalein are used. Out of the two carboxyl groups present on two different carbon atoms in GSH, one is neutralised by the presence of amino group on the same carbon atom containing the carboxyl group, while the other is titrated along with the acid liberated in the course of the reaction with mercuric chloride. Each molecule of GSH hence corresponds to two equivalents of alkali; thus permitting determination of GSH at micro level. It may be noted that although amperometric procedure with silver nitrate is quite sensitive, the reaction mixture should be protected from aerial oxidation. Furthermore, neighbouring amino and carboxyl groups may cause positive error.

The oxidimetric determination of GSH, cystine and methionine involves titration with potassium iodate in 4–5 M hydrochloric acid medium when iodate is reduced to I⁺ ion. The equivalent weight of potassium iodate in these titrations is one-fourth of its molecular weight as against one-sixth in cases using low acidity¹⁵. The end-point is quite sharp even with 0.0025 M potassium iodate as the titrant.

The number of equivalents consumed per gm-mole of reductant (Table 2) show that in GSH and cystine, the oxidation results in the formation of sulphonic acids whereas in the case of methionine the product is a sulphone.

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A Rapid Oxidimetric Determination of Psychotropic Drugs with Cerium(IV)†

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MEPAZINE hydrochloride (MH), perazine dimalonate (PDM) and propionyl promazine phosphate (PPP) belong to phenothiazine class of drugs, which are widely used for the treatment of patients with emotional or mental disorders.

A number of methods^{1–6} are known for the assay of phenothiazines but they are either time consuming or reagents used are not always readily available. Farkas and Kraaznai⁷, Blazek⁸, and Agrawal and Blake⁹ have determined phenothiazines by oxidation with cerium(IV). A comprehensive survey of the literature revealed that no attempt was made for the determination of MH, PDM and PPP. The present paper describes the oxidimetric determination of these drugs with cerium(IV).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade unless otherwise stated. Stock solutions of MH, PDM and PPP were prepared by dissolving the requisite amount of the sample in water, standardised gravimetrically¹ and stored in a refrigerator. A 0.05 N cerium(IV) sulphate was prepared in 2N sulphuric acid and standardised titrimetrically¹⁰.

Procedures :

Determination of MH, PDM or PPP : An aliquot of the stock solution (containing up to 180 mg of MH or 300 mg of PPP) was diluted to 40 ml, 5N sulphuric acid (10 ml) was added and the mixture was titrated with 0.05 N cerium(IV) sulphate. In the

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case of PDM, upto 250 mg of substance dissolved in water (30 ml) was treated with 5 N sulphuric acid (10 ml) and isopropyl alcohol (10 ml), cooled to 15° and then titrated with cerium(IV). The end-point was indicated by the complete disappearance of the red colour.

Application of the method: Thirty tablets containing MH, PDM or PPP were crushed to a fine powder. A suitable amount of the powder was weighed accurately, dissolved in water and filtered through a quantitative filter paper. The final volume of the filtrate was adjusted to 40 ml as above and the drug content determined by the above procedure. For the analysis of injection solutions, the requisite volume of the injection solutions were transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark with water. The drug content of the solution was determined as above.

Results and Discussion

Phenothiazines react with cerium(IV) in acid medium undergoing a one-electron reversible oxidation to a red coloured radical cation, which is irreversibly oxidised to a colourless sulphoxide with the loss of one more electron according to the following mechanism¹¹:

MH, R₁ = CH₃, C₆H₅, NCH₃, R₂ = H, X = hydrochloride
 PDM, R₁ = (CH₃)₂NC₆H₄NCH₃, R₂ = H, X = dimalonate
 PPP, R₁ = (CH₃)₂N(CH₃)₂, R₂ = COCH₂CH₃, X = phosphate

Effect of acidity, temperature and isopropanol: Preliminary investigations show that accurate results are obtained in an overall sulphuric acid concentrations of 0.5–3.5 N for PPP and 0.5–2.5 N for MH at room temperature. In the titration of PDM, addition of 15–30% (v/v) isopropanol and a lowering of temperature to 15 ± 5° are necessary to achieve stoichiometric results in 0.5–3.0 N sulphuric acid. The relative error does not exceed ± 1.2%.

Effect of pill additives: In order to assess the possible analytical applications of the method, the

effect of various pill additives that often accompany the psychotropic drugs in pharmaceutical preparations were studied. It has been found that there is no interference from 30-fold excess of talc, magnesium stearate, sodium citrate and dextrose. A 20-fold excess of starch and 10-fold excess of gelatin also do not interfere.

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Comparison of Co-solvent Effects on Solvent Sublation and Bubble Aeration of Hydrophobic Organics from Aqueous Solutions

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DIFFUSED bubble aeration and solvent sublation are two processes capable of removing trace hydrophobic organics from aqueous solutions using air bubbles. In the latter process, materials are transported both in the adsorbed phase on the air bubble surface as well as in the interior of the air bubbles and deposited in an overlying immiscible organic solvent like mineral oil, while in the former process no immiscible layer is present over the water column and hence only the material transported in the interior of the bubbles are removed from the aqueous phase¹. The success of conventional bubble aeration depends solely on the volatility of the hydrophobic. On the other hand, sublation only requires that the hydrophobic prefer the air-water interface of the bubbles; hence, partly

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